

1 *(Population ecology)*

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3 **Invasive crayfish populations reduce food limitation of invasive American mink**
4 **and increase its resilience to control**

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19 **Abstract**

20 Trophic relationships between invasive species may reduce food limitation they would
21 experience relative to intact ecosystems and increase they resilience to control. Here, we
22 consider whether invasive predatory American mink are trophically subsidized by
23 invasive crayfish. We collated data from the literature on density and home range size
24 of mink populations in relation to the prevalence of crayfish in the diet of mink. We
25 then tested the hypothesis that populations of an invasive predator reach higher densities
26 and are more resilient to lethal control when they have access to super-abundant non-
27 native-prey, even in the absence of changes in density dependence hence compensatory
28 capacity. We found positive and negative relationships between crayfish contribution to
29 mink diet and home range respectively, with crayfish contribution to mink diet

30 reflecting their abundance in the ecosystem. We then explored the consequence of
31 elevated mink density by simulating a hypothetical eradication program with a constant
32 harvest in a Ricker model. We found that mink populations were more resilient to
33 harvest in the presence of crayfish. As a result, the simulated number of mink harvested
34 to achieve eradication increased by a 500% in the presence of abundant crayfish if
35 carrying capacity increased by 630 %. This led to a threefold increase in time to
36 eradication under a constant harvest and approximately 20 fold increase in the
37 cumulative management cost. Our results add to evidence of inter-specific positive
38 interactions involving invasive species and our simple model illustrates how this
39 increases management cost.

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41 **Keywords:** Trophic subsidy, Positive interactions, Introduced species, Management
42 cost, Invasibility

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52 search and analyses with advice provided by XL and SP, YM and XL wrote the
53 manuscript.

54 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

55 **Introduction**

56

57 Biological invasions are having a major impact on the Earth's biodiversity with invasive
58 non-native species disrupting the composition, organization and function of many
59 ecosystems (Mack et al. 2000; United-Nations 1996; Vitousek et al. 1996; Relyea
60 2003). It has been suggested that the invasibility of an ecosystem varies according to
61 species diversity and the properties of species interactions network in recipient
62 ecosystems (Elton 1958; Tilman 1997; Lonsdale 1999; Fridley et al. 2007), with
63 evidence that invasibility decrease with species diversity (Stachowicz et al. 1999;
64 Fargione and Tilman 2005). Nonetheless, there is growing evidence that interactions
65 can also modify the resistance of a community to invasion (Bruno et al. 2003; Bulleri et
66 al. 2008; Rodriguez-Cabal et al. 2012). For example, native species can increase the
67 fitness or population density of invasive species and *vice versa*. Lenz and Facelli (2003)
68 found that native chenopod shrubs increased the survival of the invasive stem succulent
69 *Orbea variegata* by reducing temperature and radiation, whereas Tablado et al. (2010)
70 observed how the invasive red swamp crayfish *Procambarus clarkii* increased the
71 abundance of native vertebrate predators by reducing food limitation. Accordingly,
72 interactions between invasive species in multiply-invaded ecosystems can also lead to
73 interactions whereby one invader positively affects the population of the other. Indeed,
74 *in extremis*, interactions between invasive species can lead to synergetic effects and
75 invasional meltdowns, whereby entire communities are reorganized by cascades of
76 successive invasions (see Simberloff and Von Holle 1999; Simberloff 2006).

77 Attempting to restore multiply-invaded ecosystems is challenging because the
78 functional roles of species and the structure of the system have been altered (Zavaleta et

79 al. 2001; Bull and Courchamp 2009). Indeed, removing one of several established
80 invasive species may result in unpredictable and sometimes undesirable outcomes (Bull
81 and Courchamp 2009; Courchamp et al. 2003). For example, the removal of feral cats
82 *Felis catus* in Macquarie Island increased the abundance of rabbits *Oryctolagus*
83 *cuniculus* leading to substantial local and landscape-scale reduction of native vegetation
84 (Bergstrom et al. 2009). Management failures focused on single invaders resulting from
85 overlooking the interactions between invasive species, have led to poor return from
86 investment in some eradication attempts and perpetuated a sense of pessimism about the
87 scope to reverse the tide of invasions (e.g. Roemer et al. 2002; Bergstrom et al. 2009;
88 Kessler 2011). Indeed, managing established invasive species is expensive as estimated
89 as US \$ ca 22 thousand million annually in the United States alone (Pimentel et al.
90 2005). Thus current best practice in management planning includes explicit
91 consideration of potential interactions between invasive species (Bull and Courchamp
92 2009; Veitch et al. 2012; Kuebbing et al. 2013; Simberloff et al. 2013).

93 One invasive species that is established in multiply-invaded ecosystems and is
94 the focus of much control effort is the American mink *Neovison vison* (mink hereafter;
95 see Bonesi and Palazon 2007). The species is native to North America (Dunstone 1993)
96 but it is now established as an invasive species in much of Europe, southern South
97 America, China and northern Japan following escapes from fur farms (Jeschke and
98 Strayer 2005; Bonesi and Palazon 2007; see supplementary material Figure S1). It is
99 currently included amongst the worst invasive alien species threatening biodiversity and
100 native wildlife in Europe (Anon 2007) with at least 47 native species badly affected by
101 its generalist feeding behavior concentrated along riparian and coastal corridors
102 (Genovesi et al. 2012). Similar negative effects have been seen in South America (e.g.
103 Schuttler et al. 2008; Ibarra et al 2009). In its invaded range, American mink co-exists

104 with established non-native prey species with some evidence of both exploitative and
105 positive interactions. Mink spread in Poland coincided with a collapse in non-native but
106 long established muskrat populations, a favored prey of mink in its native range
107 (Errington 1943), owing to the higher density muskrats achieve themselves outside their
108 native range, possibly combined with a loss of anti predator avoidance (Brzeziński et al.
109 2010). The coexistence of mink and naturalized European rabbits in Scotland leads to a
110 pattern of predator mediated apparent competition between rabbits and native water
111 voles (Oliver et al. 2009). Studies in Catalonia by Melero et al. (2008) point to a
112 potential strong interaction between mink and non-indigenous crayfish species (NICS
113 hereafter), with mink diet dominated by NICS but crayfish populations seemingly un-
114 affected and persisting at high density. Indeed, based on the prevalence NICS in mink
115 diet in Ireland, Smal (1991) suggested that the availability of crayfish could be a major
116 determinant of mink density.

117 Here we evaluate the hypothesis that NICS trophically subsidize mink
118 populations outside their native range through reduced food limitation and consequently
119 elevated mink densities in the presence of NICS. In order to assist with prioritization of
120 mink control programs, we also explore to what extent subsidized mink populations are
121 more resilient to lethal control and how control cost would have to be escalated to
122 contend with mink population subsidized by NICS. Using published data, we ask (Q1)
123 whether the prevalence of crayfish in mink diet correlates with crayfish abundance and
124 origin (native or NICS); (Q2) whether this prevalence correlates with mink population
125 carrying capacity by increasing mink density and reducing home range sizes; (Q3)
126 whether mink populations are more resilient to control/eradication with higher carrying
127 capacity; and, if so, (Q4); whether there is also a related increase in terms of economic

128 investment and animal welfare cost (number of harvested mink) even in the absence of
129 change in compensation through density dependence.

130

131 **Materials and methods**

132

133 Literature review

134

135 Given the many studies on mink diet and ranging behavior, we searched the literature to
136 answer Q1 using combinations of keywords related to crayfish abundance, distribution
137 and origin; and mink diet, home range and density. For example, for searching
138 information on mink diet we used “*diet*” OR “*trophic*” OR “*Feed**” AND “*mink*” OR
139 “*vison*”. We gathered information from the peer-reviewed and grey literature via Web
140 of Knowledge v5.5 (Thomson Reuters, 2012) and Google Scholar search engine. We
141 also used the inventories of DAISIE (Delivering Alien Invasive Species Inventories for
142 Europe; www.europe-aliens.org), GISIN (Global Invasive Species Information
143 Network, <http://www.gisin.org>) the IUCN (<http://www.iucn.org/>). We matched studies
144 of mink diet with information on mink density, mink home range and crayfish
145 abundance data where possible.

146 The most commonly used methods to characterize carnivore diet are the relative
147 frequency of occurrence of a particular prey item (total number of occurrences of the
148 item divided by the total number of items found) and the percentage of occurrence in
149 scats. We used the relative frequency of occurrence of crayfish in mink diet (RFO
150 hereafter) for our analyses as it provides more accurate information about the relative
151 contribution of prey items. However, some studies only quoted percentage of
152 occurrence. In these cases, we used the studies with both data on RFO and percentage of

153 occurrence to derive a linear relationship between these and used it to calculate the
154 missing values of RFO (see next section and results). Mink, as most mammalian
155 carnivores, have intra-sexual territories such that home range size provides a good
156 estimate of territory size. Due to mink's riparian habits, its home range sizes obtained
157 from radio-telemetry are usually reported as linear kilometers of watercourse used,
158 which is accepted to include the riparian or shore area. Thus we did not use studies that
159 did not report home ranges in this manner (see supplementary material Table S2). Male
160 and female mink are known to have different home range size (e.g. Birks and Linn
161 1982). Thus, we only used those studies that quoted average home range of males and
162 females separately, and included sex as a factor in order to check for sex differences in
163 the response of home range size to crayfish in mink diet. As with home ranges, mink
164 density is also reported per unit of linear length of waterways (mink/km). Thus we only
165 used average mink density from studies that expressed or allowed density calculation in
166 this manner (see supplementary material Table S2). The full data set and its related
167 references are available in the supplementary material Table S1.

168

169 Statistical analyses and modeling

170

171 *Crayfish and its contribution to mink diet*

172

173 We first evaluated the relation between RFO and percentage of occurrence in mink diet
174 using a general linear model (GLM) to predict the missing values of. We used a GLM
175 to check for variation in the contribution of crayfish to mink diet (RFO) in relation to
176 crayfish abundance and whether the relationship varied according to whether the
177 crayfish species involved was native or introduced (Q1). Little data is available on

178 crayfish abundances and most of the information was qualitative based on categories of
179 abundances (e.g. abundant, common or scarce). We thus used crayfish abundance as a
180 categorical variable. We also considered models including the interaction between
181 crayfish abundance and origin. We finally used generalized linear mixed model
182 (GLMM) to test the potential effects of RFO on mink density fitted with identity
183 (Gaussian distribution) and on home range fitted with a log link function (Poisson
184 distribution) (Q2). In addition, we also tested for any relation between home range and
185 mink density to better understand their correlation and effect on the carrying capacity.
186 Alternative models for each GLMM case were set as follow: for mink density *versus*
187 RFO, we considered models including season as factor; in the case of the home range
188 we considered models with season, sex and their interaction and related three reduced
189 nested models. Lastly, the relation of mink density with home range was also evaluated
190 in a model that included sex as factor (see supplementary material Table S3). In all
191 cases, location of each study was set as random effect to account for several studies
192 taken place at some location and control its effect on the variance of the response
193 variable. Model selection was done based on AIC.

194

195 *Modeling the effect of crayfish on mink resilience to control*

196

197 To determine whether mink populations coexisting with NICS are more resilient to
198 harvesting for eradication (Q3), we used a simple model to compare the effect of
199 simulated harvesting on mink populations with different carrying capacities (K). These
200 K were chosen based on the analyses described above. We contrasted three worst case
201 scenarios, each assuming NICS affect home range size of females, the resource-limited
202 sex, assuming no mating limitations. We used a Ricker model with constant harvesting

203 to explore the effect of fixed harvest in the three different situations (K_a, K_b, K_c). The
204 Ricker model is one of the simplest and most commonly used density-dependent,
205 discrete time single species model

206

$$207 \quad N_{t+1} = \left[(N_t - H) \exp \left[r_m \left(1 - \frac{(N_t - H)}{K_j} \right) \right] \right] - H$$

208

209 where N_t and N_{t+1} are mink population densities pre breeding in years t and $t+1$, H is a
210 constant off-take, K_j is the carrying capacity with $j=a, b, c$; and r_m is the maximum rate
211 of increase of the population. In the absence of specific information in the literature on
212 r_m for American mink, we used studies on American martens *Martes americana*, and
213 ferret *Mustela putorius furo* yielding similar values of 1.0-1.3 year⁻¹ (Fryxell et al. 1999;
214 Barlow and Norbury 2001). We used $r_m = 1.3$ in keeping with our wish to explore worst
215 case scenarios. H was set as constant, as our aim was to compare the effect of different
216 carrying capacity on (K) on residual N_t when mink populations are harvested. To
217 facilitate comparison between the three assumed equilibrium population densities
218 reflecting different prey resource (K_j), we simulated a river system 100 km long and
219 assumed identical initial and equilibrium population sizes $N_{0j} = K_j$. We then estimated
220 the minimum annual number of harvested mink ($H_{effective}$) at which the compensatory
221 potential of the mink population has been exceeded and the population starts declining
222 towards extinction. Finally, we also estimated the minimum number of harvested mink
223 per year that would lead to eradication in 9 years ($H_{time-effective}$) of project, the mean
224 duration of two LIFE projects (the EU's financial funding for environmental and nature
225 conservation projects, <http://ec.europa.eu/environment/life/>).

226 All 3 scenarios considered include a low density phase prior to eradication when
227 a decline in trapping effectiveness is expected. This could be captured by varying H .

228 However in the absence of variation in density dependence, and because our aim was to
229 compare the effect of different carrying capacities, adding this degree of realism would
230 add no insights. We thus assumed that the per capita removal cost was constant
231 irrespective of residual density as this does not affect comparing the cost of managing
232 mink at different carrying capacities (Q3). Thus for illustrative purposes we considered
233 the per capita cost of dispatching a mink as constant (Q4). With some exceptions (see
234 Bryce et al. 2011), current management projects are based on the use of professional
235 trappers (e.g. Spain, France, Germany and Poland) and, most commonly, mink are
236 dispatched by qualified veterinarians whose service contribute a fixed per mink cost. In
237 Spain we estimated this cost as 60 € per mink.

238 All statistical analyses and modeling were done using R software version 15.0.

239

240 **Results**

241

242 Crayfish and its contribution to mink diet

243

244 Twenty-four of 41 studies on mink diet also had information on density and/or home
245 range size. Of these, eight had data on both density and home range sizes, thirteen had
246 data on density but not home range sizes and only three had data on home range but not
247 on density (see supplementary material Table S1). All studies were undertaken in
248 Europe, Chile or Argentina. There were no data from Japan or China.

249 The contribution of crayfish to mink diet (RFO) was tightly linearly related to its
250 percentage of occurrence ($r^2 = 0.95$; $F_{1,10} = 231.9$, $P < 0.0001$). The formula that best
251 defined their relation, $RFO = -0.14 \pm 2.58 (SE) + (0.77 \pm 0.05 * \text{Percentage of}$
252 occurrence), was used to calculate RFO for those studies that did not report it. The

253 observed and estimated RFO of crayfish in mink diet were positively related to
254 abundance and origin of crayfish species. Crayfish contributed to mink diet with higher
255 frequency when crayfish was not native (RFO vs crayfish abundance: $F_{2,34} = 69.57$, $P <$
256 0.0001 ; and RFO vs crayfish origin: $F_{1,35} = 7.09$, $P = 0.012$; Fig. 1). The relationship
257 between crayfish abundance and RFO in mink diet was not affected mink origin (native
258 vs invasive, no interaction*RFO not retained in model selection).

259 Average mink density increased significantly with the contribution of crayfish to
260 mink diet. Populations where crayfish contributed 36.6 or more to RFO mink diet
261 reached densities higher than 0.9 mink/km (Fig. 2a, Table 1). Mink with higher
262 consumption of mink had smaller home ranges. All populations where crayfish had a
263 RFO of 59 or more in mink diet had home ranges smaller than 1 km. Males had larger
264 home ranges than female mink but the magnitude of this difference was not affected by
265 crayfish RFO (Fig. 2b, Table 1; $P = 0.2$) or seasonality (not retained in model selection).
266 Where mink had smaller home range they also reached higher density; but the
267 relationship was loglinear (Fig. 2c, Table 1) with the smallest mink home range 0.45 km
268 long.

269

270 *Modeling the effect of crayfish on mink resilience and management*

271

272 We used the minimum value of female home range size for the scenario where NICS
273 subsidized the mink population, 0.45 km yielding to $K_a = 2.22$ mink/km; and the
274 average and maximum values of the known home range of females: 1.79 km and 2.85
275 km respectively, yielding $K_b = 0.56$ and $K_c = 0.35$ mink/km respectively. Estimated
276 annual number culled leading to population decline ($H_{effective}$) differed according to the
277 assumed carrying capacity with higher values required for populations with higher

278 carrying capacity: $H_{effective} = 53$ for those populations with the highest K_a ; $H_{effective} = 14$
279 for K_b and $H_{effective} = 9$ for K_c . Time to eradication varied with $H_{effective}$ of each
280 population: culling required 30 years to achieve eradication for the scenario with the
281 highest carrying capacity, K_a but less than 11 years for the other two scenarios (Fig. 3).
282 Accordingly, the associated cost to each $H_{effective}$ until eradication increased with the
283 carrying capacities: 95.4K € for 1590 mink harvested in 30 years of management in the
284 population with K_a ; 9.2K € for 154 mink and 11 years in K_b ; and 4.9K € for 81 mink in
285 9 years in the population with K_c . Because $H_{effective}$ overcomes the compensation
286 capacity of a population, increasing the annual culling number by four female mink per
287 year for K_a and by one for K_b was sufficient to reduce time to extinction to a maximum
288 of 9 years for both. Increasing culling rate, $H_{time-effective}$ reduced the final cost to 30.8K €
289 for 513 mink harvested before eradication in K_a ; and to 8.1K € for 135 mink in K_b (Fig.
290 4).

291

292 **Discussion**

293

294 We have provided evidence of a positive effect of crayfish on mink with mink densities
295 and home range size correlated positively and negatively with the proportion of crayfish
296 in mink diet (and this with crayfish abundance). In addition, high mink carrying
297 capacities, increased mink population resilience to control as illustrated by our simple
298 model, and would also increase related management costs should eradication be
299 attempted.

300

301 *Trophic subsidies amongst invasives*

302

303 Most but not all abundant crayfish populations in our analyses were non-native but,
304 irrespective of their indigenous or non-native origin, abundant crayfish populations
305 were intensely consumed by mink (48.1-89 RFO range). In such circumstance, mink
306 take up small home ranges and reach higher densities than if their carrying capacity was
307 set at a lower level by food limitation. NICS subsidize mink populations by increasing
308 prey biomass/profitability and hence reducing food limitation.

309 The elevated densities of mink populations increased their resilience to
310 simulated control (higher $H_{effective}$) and the costs of simulated eradication. The model
311 that led to this insight does of course leave out too much detail of both mink biology
312 and response to harvesting, such as a hypothetical impact of crayfish abundance on the
313 form of density dependence. It does not provide a quantitative assessment of the level of
314 harvest required to eliminate any real mink population. Thus, it should not be used for
315 such objective. However, our simple model illustrates an increase of mink resilience
316 from a modest annual harvest effort of 9 female mink/year/100 km in the population
317 with low carrying capacity (K_c) to achieve eradication to an almost 500% increase of
318 female mink harvested /year/100km in the population with higher carrying capacity
319 (K_a). This results in a threefold increase in time to eradication and an approximately
320 twenty fold increase in the cumulative management cost.

321 NICS most often achieve higher carrying capacities than native crayfish and are
322 currently widely distributed (Gherardi et al. 2011). Our analyses suggest that those areas
323 already invaded by NICS but not yet reached by mink are more susceptible to its
324 invasion. Once established, our models predict that eradicate mink will be challenging.
325 Such scenario is unfolding in northern Portugal, where the red swamp crayfish is an
326 abundant invasive species (Holdich 2002; Holdich et al. 2010) and mink is currently
327 arriving from nearby areas (Rebelo et al. 2012). Another consequence of small home

328 range size in areas where mink coexist with abundant crayfish is the production of
329 larger number of dispersers unable to obtain a territory, the process implicitly
330 responsible for density dependence in our simulations. Emigration from areas where
331 mink and crayfish coexist could lead to increase mink invasion pressure of surrounding
332 areas, irrespective of their invasion status by crayfish. Furthermore, NICS may invade
333 areas following mink and we predict this would result in elevated mink densities. For
334 example, signal crayfish *Pacifastacus leniusculus* have recently been introduced in
335 northern Scotland (Peay et al. 2006) where mink are long established (National
336 Biodiversity Network 2013) but effectively controlled as part of community led
337 conservation efforts (Bryce et al. 2011).

338

339 *Management implications*

340

341 In terms of management planning, depressing crayfish density might seem an option but
342 it is not currently feasible. Areas with high abundant NICS are typically not a priority
343 for conservation investment because, during their management, fresh water biodiversity
344 is heavily degraded. Controlling these invasive decapods is exceptionally challenging as
345 they spread fast and have enormous compensatory capacity, such that they appear
346 inexpugnable when established (Gherardi et al. 2011). Indeed, we know of no
347 successful eradication and containment attempts through e.g. barriers to dispersal are
348 necessarily short-term and local solutions. Besides, should it become feasible to
349 eradicate NICS over meaningful scales, this should be accompanied with effort to
350 mitigate the risk of a short term increase in mink predation on native preys, owing to its
351 generalist predator behavior.

352 To conclude, given that funding constrains management actions, restoration
353 attempts should focus on areas where invasive crayfish are not abundant and they
354 should be prioritized for mink control since for the moment mink can be removed with
355 reasonable investment but not crayfish. When the management aim is to prevent mink
356 from spreading further, proximity to areas where mink coexist with abundant crayfish
357 should be considered as a factor that will increase the risk of mink invasion. Indeed
358 mink emigration spilling out from areas invaded by NCIS areas will be high.
359 Furthermore, leaving incipient crayfish invasions un-managed, as is presently the case
360 in northern Scotland, risks making mink control unpractical over large surrounding
361 areas in the future. Lastly, we also guard with this study against the risk of estimating
362 the cost of management actions by extrapolating it from other previous projects if their
363 ecological context differ; e.g. using the eradication cost of mink populations preying on
364 native prey only as an estimation for population subsidized by non native crayfish.
365 Simplistic as it is, our model reinforces the value of ecological understanding in
366 informing management practice.

367

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374

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Table 1 Results for the best GLMM models on the effects of the relative frequency of occurrence (RFO) of crayfish in mink diet on mink density (mink/km) and home range (km), and between home range and mink density. Data was gathered by means of literature review on mink diet, home range and density (see supplementary material Table S1). In all cases, location of each study was set as random effect to account for several studies taken place at some location and control its effect on the variance of the response variable (see supplementary material Table S1 for the list of locations). NICS stands for non-indigenous crayfish species. Model selection was done based on AIC (see supplementary material Table S3).

Response variable	Factor	Estimate	SE	P-value (Ho Estimate = 0)
Mink density	Intercept	0.33	0.09	0.006
	Log(RFO)	0.19	0.04	0.013
Log(Home range)	Log(RFO)	-0.35	0.10	0.009
	Sex Female	1.09	0.23	0.002
	Sex Male	1.65	0.14	0.005
Mink density	Log(Home range)	-0.35	0.10	0.018
	Sex Female	0.86	0.09	<0.0001
	Sex Male	1.04	0.09	0.11

Fig. 1 Contribution of crayfish to American mink *Neovion vison* diet expressed as relative frequency of occurrence (RFO) and in relation to (a) crayfish abundance: abundant (n = 12), common (n = 8) or scarce (n = 19); and (b) crayfish origin: NICS (n = 14) or native (n = 25). RFO vs crayfish abundance: $F_{2,34} = 69.57$, $P < 0.0001$; and RFO vs crayfish origin: $F_{1,35} = 7.09$, $P = 0.012$. Boxes represent the data contained between the lower and upper quartile, inside the solid black lines indicates the median, dashed lines indicate minimum and maximum values, circles indicate outliers

Fig. 2 Log linear relationships of (a) mink density (mink/km); and (b) mink home range size (km) in relation to contribution of crayfish to mink diet expressed as RFO; and (c) mink density (mink/km) in relation to mink home range (km). Grey stands for female, black for male in (b) and (c). Continuous line relates to best model fit, dashed lines relate to the 95% confident intervals

Fig. 3 Change in mink population size (N) trough time (year) modelled in the three populations with different carrying capacity: (a) $K_a = 2.22$, (b) $K_b = 0.56$ and (c) $K_c = 0.35$ mink/km; and with a set of different number of mink captures per year (H) including the minimum H that leads to eradication ($H_{effective}$)

Fig. 4 Cumulative cost in thousand of Euros and cumulative number of harvested mink for the $H_{effective}$ and $H_{time-effective}$ of the three mink populations modelled $K_a = 2.22$, $K_b = 0.56$ and $K_c = 0.35$ mink/km. The dot at the end of the lines indicates eradication has been achieved